

Engine for growth: Uses of social media by salespeople for B2B customer generation

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ABSTRACT

As social media continues to transform the business landscape, its adoption in the business-to-business (B2B) sector remains a critical area of exploration. While business-to-consumer (B2C) enterprises have leveraged social media for customer engagement, brand building, and sales growth, the B2B context presents unique challenges and opportunities.

This paper tries to circumscribe the impact of social media strategies on generating customers within business-to-business (B2B) environments. Previous studies often focused on general brand awareness and engagement, while this paper focuses more on the social selling aspect. Social selling depends mainly on 2 factors: organizational strategy regarding social selling and companies' individual salesperson selling activities. Within this paper, semi-structured interviews are conducted with salespeople. This mainly looks at how social media helps salespeople selling performance using social media. Social media mainly has 3 roles in this: 1) Acquisition of customer insights 2) connecting consumers 3) creating involvement. This paper focuses more on the individual aspects of the salesperson. Main arguments arising from this paper is that the individual use of social media has a positive effect on individual selling performance.

The findings contribute to both academic knowledge and practical applications, offering insights for B2B enterprises aiming to integrate social media into their digital transformation strategies. Future research can provide a more grounded analysis as to how social media channels can leverage these different aspects.

Keywords

B2B, Social Media, Advertising, Digital Platforms

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, social media has reshaped how businesses engage with customers, creating new opportunities for interaction, brand development, and market expansion (Ancillai et al., 2019). Although widely utilized in business-to-consumer (B2C) environments, social media adoption in business-to-business (B2B) settings presents unique challenges and opportunities. These challenges can be the negative connotations associated with advertising on social media resulting and limited reach that ads that focus on B2B sales resulting in a lower return on investment (ROI) compared to traditional marketing

For B2B companies, social media serves not only as a visibility tool but as a means for strategic customer acquisition and relationship-building through "social selling" (Terho et al., 2022). Social selling enables sales professionals to leverage social platforms to gain customer insights, connect with clients, and foster ongoing engagement—elements critical to successful sales performance in today's digital business landscape (Terho et al., 2022).

The potential of social selling lies in its ability to streamline B2B interactions through insight acquisition, client connection, and engagement creation (Agnihotri et al., 2016). However, limited research has explored how individual sales professionals' social media usage directly impacts sales outcomes. This report aims to explore how individual social selling practices influence B2B sales performance, focusing specifically on small to medium-sized consultancy firms in information management. By examining social media as a digital platform, this study aims to uncover how personal use of social media by sales professionals contributes to improved sales outcomes through targeted social selling activities.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

While there is substantial research on B2B social media strategies aimed at brand awareness and general engagement (Ancillai et al., 2019), there is a lack of focus on the role of individual sales professionals in this space. Current studies have primarily examined social media's effect on overall brand image and customer engagement rather than investigating how personal engagement by salespeople might directly influence sales outcomes (Terho, 2022). This oversight leaves a gap in understanding how personal social media usage affects customer acquisition and relationship-building within B2B contexts.

This study addresses this knowledge gap by investigating how the individual social media activities of sales professionals—such as gaining customer insights, building connections, and maintaining client engagement—contribute to sales performance (Koponen & Rytty, 2020; Weng et al., 2024). Through this focused exploration, the research seeks to expand both academic understanding and practical applications of social selling in B2B environments.

METHOD

The authors have chosen to conduct research of an explorative, qualitative nature into social media usage for B2B sales. Qualitative research is considered as “indispensable tool for garnering deep insights and understanding complex phenomena” (Lim, 2024). Gathering deep insights into social media usage for B2B sales by IT consultants enables the researchers to understand how social media usage does affect sales and which steps IT consultants undertake and why. Within this research paper, semi-structured interviews are conducted with respondents working for small to medium sized IT consulting firms (<250 FTE) in the Netherlands.

According to Albaret & Deas (2023), semi-structured interviews are considered “a qualitative research method that consists of collecting data on facts and representations discovered during oral exchanges.” Semi-structured interviews enable the researchers to reconstruct courses of events and/or decision making and can be relevant to study hard-to-reach fields (Albaret & Deas, 2023). In short, in a semi-structured interview, the interviewer undergoes various topics to which the interviewee is questioned about. The topics have been predefined before the interview in a topic list, which is to be used by all interviewers. The topic list (appendix A) encompasses topics which have

emerged from the theoretical framing and ensure that all interviewers have a guide path for their interview. After an interview is conducted, the coding will take place in which the researchers transcribe and attach codes to pieces of the transcription. Coding allows the researchers to organize the data, compare data and integrate data further for conceptual and/or theoretical analysis (Gibbs 2018). The product which will be used in the results section encompasses useful extracts from the interviews (codes) which subsequently are used by the researchers to link empirical findings with existing theory or expectations.

What are the limitations of the methods used? First and foremost, the data that is collected from the researchers can be “subjective and imprecise” (Rathbun 2008: 685). These implications arise from the nature of the semi-structured interview which can be steered by the interviewer. Because the interviewer can steer the interviewee in questioning and subsequently answering questions, biases can occur in the data collection phase. Also, qualitative research methods are recognized for its capabilities to gather deep insights and understanding phenomena, but as a clear downside the insights cannot represent an entire population (Lim, 2024). Qualitative research is mostly only capable of generalizing insights generated, which can be researched with different methods in future research. Lastly, from a practical perspective, the research effort is limited to time and resource constraints. The researchers only have a limited timespan to conduct the data collection, analysis and interpretation, and therefore only a limited number of interviews have been conducted.

RESEARCH QUESTION

The primary research question in this study is: "How does individual social media usage by sales professionals' impact B2B sales performance in small-to-medium information management consultancy firms?"

To address this question, the study will examine three related sub-questions:

- How does social media usage contribute to customer insight acquisition for sales professionals in B2B consultancy?
- In what ways do social media platform features facilitate the connection and engagement between sales professionals and potential clients?

- What role do social media interactions play in maintaining ongoing client relationships and enhancing engagement?

These questions aim to explore the specific dimensions of social selling—insight acquisition, connection, and engagement—while considering the unique digital platform elements of social media that can drive client acquisition and retention within the B2B consultancy context (Terho, 2022).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The use of social media by sales professionals is defined as follows: “any social interaction enhancing technology that can be deployed by sales professionals to generate content and develop networks” (Agnihotri et al., 2012, cited in Agnihotri, 2016). When companies aim to reach new customers through social media, this practice is known as “social selling” (Ancillai et al., 2019). Social selling is a sales method defined as a practice “which leverages social channels for understanding, connecting with, and engaging influencers, prospects, and existing customers at relevant customer journey touchpoints for building valuable business relationships” (Terho et al., 2022). Given the broad definition of this construct, Terho et al. (2022) categorizes social selling as a three-dimensional construct comprising i) insight acquisition, ii) connecting, and iii) engagement.

The first component, insight acquisition, focuses on how social media can be used to gather information on prospective and current customers. It emphasizes social media’s potential to improve understanding of customer needs and uncover market opportunities by offering insights into customer demand (Terho et al., 2022). The second component, connecting, underscores the role of social media in building and maintaining networks through activities such as chatting, commenting, and responding to both personal and others’ content (Terho et al., 2022). The third component, engagement, highlights how social media keeps customers and other stakeholders involved with the organization by sharing relevant content (Terho et al., 2022).

Together, these three components within the “social selling” construct enable salespeople to influence (potential) customers to invest resources such as time and attention, thereby establishing a foundation for future customer relationships, an important factor given that today’s customers are increasingly well-informed (Holliman & Rowley, 2014, cited in Terho et al., 2022).

The social selling construct has potential outcomes on the selling performance of a salesperson (Terho

et al., 2022). These outcomes, that make up the construct of Salesperson selling performance, consist of three separate dimensions that measures the effectiveness of a salesperson. The first dimension, better lead quality and lead attractiveness, focusses on the internal value of an individual lead. This can be measured in the likelihood of converting a lead into a customer Wu, Andreev, and Benyoucef (2024). The second dimension is sales process efficiency. This consists of the length of the sales cycle and the closing ratio that a salesperson achieves Terho et al., (2022). The third component is revenue. This component is the clearest measurement for determining the performance of a salesperson over an extended period Terho et al. (2022).

This paper examines the effects of social media, specifically the impact of social selling, on sales performance within the B2B context. The theoretical framework underlying this research question is social presence theory. Social presence theory posits that social presence is a “multidimensional construct, including social presence of the communication medium, the perception of others, and the social presence of interaction between supplier and customer” (Weng et al., 2024). Koponen & Rytsy (2020) identified three key dimensions of social presence theory within a B2B setting: interactive social presence, affective social presence, and relationship maintenance social presence.

The first dimension, interactive social presence, emphasizes that social interactions on social media can foster trust between organizations. These interactions provide customers with feedback, thereby increasing their confidence in the company’s services and products (Agnihotri et al., 2016). The second dimension, affective social presence, encourages the expression of positive and negative emotions on social media through likes and comments, which strengthens relationships and builds mutual trust within the B2B sector (Weng et al., 2024). The final dimension, relationship maintenance social presence, suggests that social media facilitates the easy maintenance of relationships (Weng et al., 2024).

Because the key dimensions of social presence theory in B2B, as defined by Koponen & Rytsy (2020), align closely with the constructs of social selling proposed by Terho et al. (2022), this theory can offer new insights into how sales professionals might leverage social media to enhance performance. This can provide insight into which aspects of social selling influence the sales performance of salespeople

RESULTS

In analysing the interviews (N=2), the themes were structured around the dimensions of social selling. By combining the exploratory nature of the research with the theoretical framework of social selling dimensions, clear insights were generated into how social selling operates within a B2B context. Consequently, the themes in the results were organized according to the three dimensions of social selling as formulated by Terho et al. (2022): insight acquisition, connecting, and engagement.

This thematic structure (Appendix B) allowed for a focused examination of how each individual dimension of social selling impacts the three performance dimensions: lead quality, efficiency, and revenue. Specifically, the analysis explored the effects of insight acquisition, connecting, and engagement on these performance outcomes. Additionally, the study investigated whether social presence theory could help explain the relationships between these dimensions, thereby offering a richer understanding of the mechanisms underlying these connections.

The first finding that has been in scope is “Respondents who strongly focus on insight acquisition generally possess a better understanding of their clients' customer preferences.” As one respondent explained:

"We rely heavily on word-of-mouth referrals and partnerships with large platforms. We are exploring ways to specifically target regions with interesting companies. However, after analysing Google search data, we found that monthly search volumes related to our sector in the Netherlands were under 500. This means we have to deviate from Google and focus more on offline activities for now."

Another respondent added:

"Referrals are the most important for us. We maintain close relationships with key account managers at large partner organizations. Additionally, we have developed numerous case studies that provide tangible examples for prospective clients."

Despite this reliance on offline methods, organizations must possess sufficient knowledge of social media to guide their clients in reaching their customers effectively. Data collected through social media is carefully analysed, stored, and compared across similar organizations to identify best practices. This approach enables these B2B firms to operate more effectively by applying proven strategies.

Furthermore, transparency in presenting these findings plays a crucial role in converting leads. As one respondent noted:

"We process all client data in Databox, where we create dashboards to visualize possible outcomes and results. These insights help us compare the performance of campaigns across different companies and regions. This allows us to provide clients with transparent recommendations about what will or won't work in their specific context. Our transparency is one of the reasons companies are eager to collaborate with us."

One respondent highlighted a notable shift from "professional platforms" to what they referred to as "general platforms":

"LinkedIn is, of course, very effective for professional purposes, but within our sector, we're seeing a gradual shift toward more general META platforms. For example, we recently received a direct message from an organization through one of these platforms. Personally, I believe we'll see a move from LinkedIn toward broader social media platforms. These platforms also streamline communication, bypassing reception desks and enabling direct contact."

The interviews revealed that B2B organizations primarily offer advisory services to their clients on the type of content to share to effectively reach their own consumers. However, the organizations themselves are less active in sharing relevant content on their own social media channels.

This was evident from the following respondent's statement:

"We manage campaigns on behalf of our clients. We begin by analysing the client's concept and the experience they want to convey. Then, we determine the best approach—whether that's a product-focused strategy or a video, depending on the client's business stage."

Another respondent added:

"Before we launch anything, we always send the materials for approval—texts, headlines, and how they will be integrated into a CRM system. The clients can provide feedback, and if we think something isn't marketing-wise optimal, we point it out. Sometimes, the most effective phrasing depends on the region and the language nuances."

DISCUSSION

Interpretation

In summary, B2B organizations use their knowledge of social media less for their own lead generation but more as a tool to improve the services they offer to their clients. Based on these findings, three key insights have been identified:

1. Respondents who strongly focus on insight acquisition generally possess a better understanding of their clients' customer preferences.
2. A strong focus on insight acquisition hints to improved lead quality, as these respondents are more likely to convert leads into customers.
3. Indirectly, respondents with a strong focus on insight acquisition achieve higher revenue, as the likelihood of converting leads into customers is increased.

The first theme, insight acquisition, focuses on how social media can be leveraged to gather information about both prospective and existing customers. It highlights the potential of social media to enhance understanding of customer needs and identify market opportunities by providing valuable insights into customer demand (Terho et al., 2022). The interviews revealed that social media is predominantly used by B2B organizations to gather information about the potential customers of their own clients. However, these organizations primarily rely on referrals and word-of-mouth advertising for acquiring new business. This implies that organizations use social media for their acquisition of new customers, however that it should not be seen as their sole source of obtaining new customers. As social media can be part of their consultancy business, having proper knowledge about the platforms is key and that knowledge can be reused in questions posed by customers. However, businesses are still much reliant on different forms of acquisition, especially in niche markets.

The second theme, connecting, emphasizes the role of social media in fostering and maintaining networks through activities such as messaging, commenting, and responding to content, both personal and shared (Terho et al., 2022). From the interviews, it became apparent that social media primarily accelerates communication between B2B organizations. While the interviewed organizations do not advertise directly on social media, the platforms facilitate faster connections. The businesses that have been interviewed tend to use social media after the customer has been acquired. Social media is deemed useful for staying connected with the customer and to showcase progress to the customer. The content that is produced on the social media platforms are also

subject to review, as some products are portrayed on social media platforms.

The third theme, engagement, explores how organizations utilize social media to maintain involvement with customers and other stakeholders by sharing relevant content (Terho et al., 2022). In other words, how can social media play a role in B2B sales? The interviews, however, did not reveal direct evidence that maintaining networks via social media has a measurable impact on lead quality, efficiency, or revenue. Nonetheless, based on the interviews, one key finding has been formulated:

4. Connecting contributes to a faster conversion cycle, which suggests improved efficiency.

This implies that when organizations seek a connection with their target customer, another business, using social media can be a tool for these organizations to connect with their target consumer and to accelerate their acquisition of new businesses.

Based on the interviews, a table (see Appendix B) and conceptual model were developed to visually represent the direct (straight line) and indirect (dotted line) findings between social selling and performance. The findings clearly indicate that insight acquisition is the most critical dimension of social selling in the B2B context relative to performance outcomes. Insight acquisition provides information about the results clients can expect when implementing strategies previously tested with other customers. This knowledge enables salespeople to more effectively convert leads into customers, suggesting that insight acquisition positively influences both lead quality and revenue. Furthermore, social media's role in facilitating faster connections with other organizations was highlighted as a key benefit. This acceleration of contact shortens the conversion cycle from lead to customer, indicating improved efficiency.

Limitations

The main aim of this study was to establish a deeper understanding of how social media usage impacted B2B sales performance in small-to-medium sized information management consulting firms. During this research effort, two interviews (N=2) have been conducted by the researchers. Gathering deep-dive insights are useful to understand the phenomena surrounding social media usage driving B2B sales performance. As the information is qualitative of nature, the data is difficult to quantify and cannot be subject to statistical analyses or causal analysis to validate theories. The time scope of this research effort was

limited, and as such only shorter interviews were conducted. Also, because of the time constraint, only two interviews were conducted. Having less interviews which are also shorter in time have the implication of less in-depth data to be analysed and less data excerpts to compare. Having less data excerpts to compare limits this research effort into fully conceptualizing the phenomena surrounding social media usage in B2B sales.

Because the interviewed organizations primarily supported their clients' social media strategies rather than actively engaging on their own platforms, no conclusions could be drawn about the impact of engagement on performance metrics within a B2B context. Specifically, there was no interaction with their own content to measure its effectiveness. Concluding, this research effort is only able to assess how these consulting firms assist other businesses' efforts in sales performance but is limited in explaining how B2B sales performance is influenced by social media.

Another limitation of this research is, due to the limited time and respondents, the decision was made to not separate the research questions for different social media platforms. Especially the impact of advertising on a platform focussed on professionals compared to a broader social media platform like Instagram may have large implications for the results when more respondents are used. In future research this separation is recommended.

Conclusion

This study examined the impact of individual social media usage by sales professionals on B2B sales performance in small-to-medium information management consultancy firms, emphasizing the roles of insight acquisition, connecting, and engagement.

The findings underscore the critical importance of social selling in driving sales outcomes, with insight acquisition emerging as the most impactful dimension. Sales professionals who actively leverage social media to gather customer insights demonstrate a better understanding of customer preferences and market opportunities, leading to higher lead quality, greater lead attractiveness, and improved revenue through enhanced conversion rates.

Additionally, social media platforms enable faster and more efficient connections with potential clients, accelerating the sales process by shortening conversion cycles and enhancing sales process efficiency. Although engagement activities—such

as maintaining customer involvement through shared content—play a role in fostering ongoing client relationships, this study did not find direct evidence linking engagement to improved sales metrics. These findings reinforce the value of social media as a strategic tool for enhancing individual sales performance, particularly when aligned with broader digital transformation strategies in B2B contexts.

Given the qualitative nature of this study and its reliance on a limited number of interviews, future research should explore these findings through quantitative methods to assess the broader effects of social selling on B2B acquisition. Longitudinal studies could provide deeper insights into the long-term impacts of social media usage on client retention and revenue, while further exploration of the integration of social media platform features into customer relationship management systems could enhance understanding of their contribution to improving sales performance.

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APPENDIXES:

Appendix A:

Topic list for semi-structured interviews

1. Introduction and Context

- Brief explanation of the research objectives and structure.
- Background information about the interviewee and their role within the company.
- Experiences with social media usage in the context of sales.
- How do you perceive the impact of social media usage on sales performance in general?

2. Social Media Usage for Enhancing Salesperson Effectiveness

2.1 Lead Quality and Attractiveness

- How does social media impact the quality and attractiveness of the leads you generate?
- Which social media platforms do you primarily use to gather customer information?
- How does social media help you gain insights into customer needs, preferences, and behaviors?
- What social media strategies or activities do you believe contribute to generating higher-quality leads?
- Can you provide specific examples where social media usage has led to valuable customer insights?
- Can you provide examples of how social media has helped increase the likelihood of converting a lead into a customer?
- How do you measure or evaluate the attractiveness of leads acquired through social media?
- What role does social media play in maintaining relationships with existing clients?

- How does social media use contribute to staying in regular contact with existing customers, without seeming intrusive?
- How are social media platforms used to keep customers involved with your company for the long term, and which platform functionalities help the most with this?

2.2 Sales Process Efficiency

- In what ways does social media influence the efficiency of your sales process?
- Which social media platform features (such as LinkedIn, Twitter) are most useful for establishing connections with potential clients?
- How important are direct messaging, comments, or content sharing for creating connections with prospects?
- To what extent does receiving feedback via social media influence your view of customer needs and your approach in sales conversations?
- Have you observed any reductions in the length of your sales cycle due to social media engagement?
- Does social media interaction contribute to improving your closing ratio? If so, how?
- Are there specific social media tools or features that have helped streamline your sales process?

2.3 Revenue Performance

- How does social media usage impact your overall revenue performance over time?
- Have you noticed revenue growth as a result of consistent social media interactions?
- What role do social media strategies play in achieving sustained sales and revenue outcomes?
- How do you evaluate the contribution of social media to long-term revenue performance?

3. Impact of Social Media Usage on Sales Performance

- What specific benefits do you think the use of social media has for sales performance? (E.g. improved customer engagement, faster response to customer queries, increased trust)
- Have you noticed that social media usage has delivered specific results, such as shorter sales cycles or higher conversion rates?
- In your view, what are the key advantages of social media usage for sales in your sector?

- What obstacles do you encounter when using social media to improve sales performance?

4. Future Opportunities and Challenges

- How do you see the future role of social media in B2B sales within small-to-medium consultancy firms?
- What changes or trends do you anticipate in how sales professionals will use social media?
- Are there any training or resources you would find helpful to further optimize social media usage for sales?

5. Conclusion

- Additional thoughts or comments on social media usage in sales.
- Any recommendations for best practices for other sales professionals in your sector.

APPENDIX B: THEME TABLE

THEME	DIMENSION SOCIAL SELLING	LINKED TO WHICH DIMENSION PERFORMANCE	EXPLANATION
INSIGHT ACQUISITION	INSIGHT ACQUISITION	INDIRECT TO LEAD QUALITY AND REVENUE	A STRONG FOCUS ON GAINING INSIGHTS INDICATES IMPROVED LEAD QUALITY, AS THESE RESPONDENTS ARE MORE LIKELY TO CONVERT LEADS INTO CUSTOMERS. THEREFORE, SALESPEOPLE WHO FOCUS ON GAINING INSIGHTS CAN ACHIEVE HIGHER SALES BECAUSE THEY ARE MORE LIKELY TO CONVERT LEADS INTO CUSTOMERS.
CONNECTING	CONNECTING	EFFICIENCY	CONNECTING CONTRIBUTES TO A FASTER CONVERSION CYCLE, SUGGESTING IMPROVED EFFICIENCY
ENGAGEMENT	ENGAGEMENT		THE RESULTS FOUND NO DIRECT OR INDIRECT FINDINGS

APPENDIX C: MODEL

Appendix D: Letter to reviewers

Dear reviewers,

First, we would like to thank you for the time you've taken in reviewing the abstract for our paper. The feedback that you have provided to us has been invaluable in finalizing our research and the writing of the final paper.

In the following list we've taken all the points that we have received and note the steps we've taken to process the feedback. If there's any questions regarding this, please do not hesitate to contact us for further details.

Names of the reviewers have been anonymized for privacy reasons.

Primary points of feedback reviewer 1:

1. There should be greater transparency in the methodology regarding the interviews. Specifically, the selection process, interview structure and data analysis should be outlined very clearly.
 - a. due to the scope this wasn't possible everywhere, but we've tried to make it as transparent as possible.
2. Outline possible future research that could expand on our current findings
 - a. Possible future research has been added to the limitations/discussion

Primary points of feedback reviewer 2:

1. Besides the positives of b2b marketing over social media also look at the possible downsides/negative effects that b2b marketing over social media can have on the sales for a company.
 - a. We added this to both the introduction as the possible future research
2. Improve the presentation with more consistent referencing and a more a clearer diagram.
 - a. Our final paper has been styled better and has an improved version of the diagram.

Primary points of feedback reviewer 3:

1. Undertake steps to mitigate the effects of the bias that a small sample size of interviewees might have on the research.
 - a. We've taken this into account in the discussion part of the paper
2. A more detailed discussion about the theories regarding the different social presence theories and how they interact with specific actions from sales employees will help make a stronger theoretical foundation.
 - a. Due to the scope of the paper, there wasn't enough room for a extensive discussion regarding these theories. It has been added as a possible future research point

Primary points of feedback reviewer 4:

1. Consider platform specific effects like LinkedIn vs Instagram
 - A. This has been added in the limitations and as possible future research
2. Provide actionable recommendations for the salespersons based on the outcome of the research
 - a. Due to the scope of the paper and the limited amount of respondents the value of such recommendations was fairly limited
3. Include findings from Andzulis et al. (2012) or Järvinen & Taiminen (2016) to address external factors like training or tool support.
 - a. due to scope, we couldn't include this. It has been noted for future research.
4. Highlight the unique contributions of this study compared to recent research.

- a. This has been addressed in the introduction of the paper

Finally, we would once again, we would like to thank you for your feedback. It has been instrumental in increasing the quality of our paper.

Sincerely,

Maurits Koot, Melvin Montizaan, Rosita Nikolova, Sven de Neve